

Microbial production of Lovastatin: a bioprospecting and green pharmaceutical approach

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Manuscript details:

Received: 09.04.2026
Accepted: 09.05.2026
Published: 30.05.2026

Cite this article as:

Shukla Shraddha, Kale Ganesh, Nagre Pavan, Gayakwad Ganesh, Jadhav Yash, Jadhav Mahadev (2026) Microbial production of Lovastatin: a bioprospecting and green pharmaceutical approach, *Int. J. of Life Sciences*, 14 (1A):157-164.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20653905>

Available online on <http://www.ijlsci.in>
ISSN: 2320-964X (Online)
ISSN: 2320-7817 (Print)

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ABSTRACT

Lovastatin, a potent inhibitor of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase, is an important cholesterol-lowering agent produced as a secondary metabolite by filamentous fungi, particularly species within the *Aspergillus* genus. While chemically synthesized statins are widely available, microbial fermentation offers a sustainable and “natural” alternative for large-scale industrial production. The objective of this study was to isolate, screen, and identify high yielding lovastatin producing fungal strains from natural sources (soil) across different regions of Maharashtra, India. Two primary isolates were selected and identified using standardized microbiological methods including morphological characterization and microscopic techniques. Production was evaluated via submerged fermentation, with preliminary screening conducted through Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), and UV spectrophotometric analysis. Confirmatory analysis was performed using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) and Attenuated total reflectance (ATR-FTIR) against a reference standard. Among the isolates, *Aspergillus terreus* (RFI) isolated from rice farm soil exhibited the highest yield 530 mg/100 ml, while *Aspergillus terreus* (RSI) from red soil also showed significant production levels 410 mg/100 ml of Czapek dox broth. This study demonstrates that a bioprospecting approach toward local fungal biodiversity provides a viable and efficient platform for green pharmaceutical manufacturing, offering a sustainable alternative to chemical synthesis for cholesterol control.

Keywords: Lovastatin, *Aspergillus terreus*, submerged fermentation, bioprospecting, Green pharmaceutical approach, HMG-CoA Reductase Inhibitor, HPLC & ATR-FTIR analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In many countries, coronary heart disease is a common cause of death in human beings. A primary physiological risk factor for the development of atherosclerosis and subsequent coronary heart disease is hypercholesterolemia, characterized by elevated levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol in the bloodstream (Alberts et al. 1980; Tobert, 2003; Endo, 1979; Barrios-González and Miranda, 2010).

The pharmacological management of this condition centers on the inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase, the rate-limiting enzyme in the mevalonate pathway of cholesterol biosynthesis (Alberts et al. 1980; Tobert, 2003; Endo, 1979). Among the various therapeutic agents developed, Lovastatin was the first statin drug approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 1987 for the treatment of hypercholesterolemia for clinical use (Tobert, 2003). Beyond its role in cholesterol control, recent studies have highlighted its potential applications in treating certain cancers, bone disorders, and fungal infections, further increasing its clinical value (Barrios-González and Miranda, 2010; Manzoni and Rollini, 2002). While chemical synthesis of statins is possible, it is often complex, expensive, and involves harsh reagents. In contrast, microbial fermentation provides a sustainable, cost-effective, and "natural" alternative for large-scale production (Barrios-González and Miranda, 2010; Manzoni and Rollini, 2002). Lovastatin is produced as a secondary metabolite by various filamentous fungi, with species of the genus *Aspergillus*, particularly *Aspergillus terreus*, being the most prolific industrial producers (Barrios-González and Miranda, 2010; Kumar et al. 2000).

Aspergillus terreus has been recognized by the FDA as one of the most suitable and efficient organism for commercial lovastatin production and remains the established industry standard (Gunde-Cimerman and Cimerman, 1995). Despite the widespread use of *A. terreus*, there is a continuous academic and industrial drive to discover novel, high-yielding strains. Bioprospecting from untapped natural habitats remains a vital strategy for identifying superior wild-type isolates with robust metabolic profiles (Kumar et al. 2000). The geographic and climatic diversity of regions like Maharashtra, India, offers a rich reservoir for microbial diversity, yet many of its local soil ecosystems remain underexplored for pharmaceutical potential.

The present study, titled "Microbial production of lovastatin: a bioprospecting and green pharmaceutical approach", focuses on the isolation and characterization of lovastatin-producing fungi from various soil types in Maharashtra, including rice farm and red soil. By employing a combination of morphological identification and advanced analytical techniques-such as TLC, HPLC, and ATR-FTIR - this

research aims to evaluate the efficiency of local fungal isolates as viable platforms for green pharmaceutical manufacturing (Barrios-González and Miranda, 2010; Upendra, et al. 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. Materials and Reagents: The chemicals and media used in this study were of analytical grade.

- **Microbiological Media:** Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), and Czapek Dox Broth were utilized for fungal maintenance and fermentation (HiMedia, India)
- **Solvents:** High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)-grade acetonitrile, methanol, and ethyl acetate were sourced for extraction and mobile phase preparation.
- **Staining Reagents:** Lactophenol Cotton Blue for microscopic identification.

2. Collection and Isolation of Fungi:

- **Sampling:** Natural soil samples were collected from various ecological niches across the Maharashtra region of India, specifically targeting rice farm soil and red soil types.
- **Isolation:** The serial dilution and spread plate technique were employed for fungal isolation
- **Cultivation:** One gram of each soil sample was suspended in 9 mL of sterile saline (0.85% NaCl) and diluted to 10^{-6} . Aliquots were inoculated onto PDA plates supplemented with antibacterial agents and incubated at 37°C for 5-7 days.

3. Identification of Strains:

- **Morphological Identification:** The fungal isolates were identified based on macroscopic colony features, including pigment production (color), colony diameter, and surface texture.
- **Microscopic Characterization:** Fungal morphology was further confirmed through Lactophenol Cotton Blue (LPCB) staining. This allowed for the detailed observation of conidial head structures, vesicle shapes, and conidia arrangements under light microscopy to confirm the genus and species.
- **Strain Selection:** Based on robust growth profiles and preliminary screening, two specific isolates were selected for further investigation: RFI (Rice Farm Isolate) and RSI (Red Soil Isolate).

Fermentation and Preliminary Screening:

Small-scale fermentation was performed using Czapek Dox medium containing, sucrose, 30 g/l; NaNO₃, 0.3 g/l; K₂HPO₄, 1 g/l; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.5 g/l; KCl, 0.5 g/l; FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.01 g/l; Yeast extract, 3 g/l. A 10 mL inoculum was added to 90 mL of the medium and incubated at 30°C for 8-10 days in a rotary shaker at 100 rpm. Preliminary screening for lovastatin production was conducted using:

- Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)
- UV Spectrophotometric Analysis

Extraction of lovastatin from screening medium:

The screening medium was filtered using filter paper to obtain the culture filtrate containing the secondary metabolite. The pH of the resulting broth was adjusted to a range of 2.0-3.0. An equal volume of ethyl acetate was added to the broth and shaken gently. The organic phase containing lovastatin was separated from the aqueous phase. To remove residual water, anhydrous sodium sulfate (a pinch per 10 mL) was added, and the mixture was shaken for 15–30 minutes. The dried ethyl acetate was then filtered and evaporated at 35 - 40°C until a crude residue was obtained. The resulting residue was re-dissolved in 1 mL of ethyl acetate and utilized as the extract for further analytical confirmation (Samiee et al. 2003).

Lovastatin Confirmation by Thin Layer Chromatography:

Extracts were spotted onto TLC plates and developed in a suitable solvent system containing toluene: ethanol in the ratio of 80:20. Chromatograms were visualized using iodine vapor, and R_f values were calculated (Srinu et al., 2010).

UV Spectrophotometric Analysis of Lovastatin:

Prepared samples were analyzed qualitatively across a range of 210nm to 350nm in triplicate. Lovastatin was detected and estimated at a λ_{\max} of 238-240nm by comparing results with reference standard values (Lingappa et al., 2004).

Confirmatory Analysis: To confirm the presence and yield of lovastatin, the fermented extracts were analyzed by:

High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

Fermented extracts were clarified through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and analyzed for lovastatin yield via High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)

using an Inertsil ODS-3 C 18 column (250×4.6 mm, 5 μ m). Chromatographic separation was achieved at 238nm with 20 μ l injection volume. The mobile phase comprised an isocratic mixture of acetonitrile and 0.1 per cent phosphoric acid (60:40 v/v) at flow rate of 1.2 ml min⁻¹ and a column temperature of 25° (Sayyad et al., 2007).

ATR-FTIR Analysis of Lovastatin:

The structural integrity and functional groups of the purified lovastatin extracted from the Rice Farm Isolate (RFI) and Red Soil Isolate (RSI) were confirmed using Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy. ATR was fitted with a single bounce diamond at 45° internally reflected incident light providing a sampling area of 1 mm in diameter with a sampling depth of several microns. A small amount of the sample was directly placed on the diamond disk and liquid sample kept in liquid sample holder. Sample was scanned for absorbance over the range from 4000 to 400 wave numbers (cm⁻¹) at a resolution of 1 cm⁻¹ (Nazzal et al., 2002).

RESULTS

Identification of Strains: In this research, two fungal colonies were isolated from different natural samples (rice farm soil and red soil) on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. These isolates were characterized using standard microbiological methods, including:

Morphological Identification:

The fungal isolates were identified based on macromorphological properties such as colony color, shape, size, margin, elevation, and growth rate (Figure 1).

Microscopic Characterization:

Following morphological identification, microscopic characterization was performed using Lactophenol Cotton Blue (LPCB) staining. Diagnostic features such as the conidial head, conidiophores, vesicles, and conidia were successfully observed (Figure 2). The identified fungal cultures were maintained in pure form on PDA slants and stored at 4°C for further use.

Lovastatin Confirmation by Thin Layer Chromatography:

The retention factor (R_f) values of the fungal extracts were determined using TLC with a solvent system of

toluene and ethanol in a ratio of 80:20. The R_f value for pure lovastatin was determined to be 0.70. The rice farm isolate (RFI) and red soil isolate (RSI) exhibited spots with R_f values of 0.66 and 0.65, respectively, which are in close agreement with the standard. The

presence of identical spots in both fungal extracts confirms that the isolated soil-derived fungi are capable of synthesizing lovastatin under optimized fermentation conditions (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Microscopic identification of *Aspergillus terreus* colonies on PDA plate showing cinnamon brown colour.

A) Rice farm isolate, B) Red soil isolate

Figure 2: Microscopic characterization of *Aspergillus terreus*; A) Rice farm isolate, B) Red soil isolate.

Fig.3: A B

Fig. 4

Figure 3: TLC profile of lovastatin. A) Rice farm isolate and B) Red soil isolate under iodine vapour visualization.
Figure 4: UV-Visible spectra of extracted lovastatin metabolites from: A) Rice farm isolate B) Red soil isolate.

HPLC Analysis of Microbial Lovastatin:

The secondary metabolite profiles of the fungal isolates were analyzed using Reverse-Phase HPLC (RP-HPLC) on a Thermo Fisher Ultimate 3000 system. Separation was achieved using a mobile phase

consisting of acetonitrile and 0.1% phosphoric acid with UV detection at 238nm, the characteristic absorption maximum for the lovastatin hexahydro-naphthalene ring system (Samiee et al.2003). The chromatogram for the Rice Farm Isolate (RFI) (Figure

5) displayed a prominent Peak 9 at a retention time (R_t : 3.14 min) with a peak height of 430.39 mAU. A secondary Peak 11 was also identified at 3.93 min with a height of 191.45 mAU. In contrast, the Red Soil Isolate (RSI) (Figure 6) exhibited its primary metabolic output at Peak 6 (R_t : 2.43 min) with a peak height of 454.65 mAU, while Peak 9 was recorded at 3.19 min with a height of 107.75 mAU. The presence of multiple peaks eluting between 2.0 and 4.0 minutes is consistent with established *Aspergillus* fermentation profiles, which typically yield a mixture of lovastatin

in its lactone and hydroxy-acid forms (Srinu et al., 2010; Ramadan et al. 2023). The variation in primary retention times (3.14 min for RFI vs. 2.43 min for RSI) is attributed to the different concentrations of these two forms produced by the respective isolates (Panda, et al. (2009). Based on the retention time alignment and characteristic UV absorbance, it is concluded that both the Rice Farm Isolate and the Red Soil Isolate successfully produce lovastatin as a secondary metabolite.

Figure.5: HPLC Chromatogram of Rice Farm Isolate

Figure.6: HPLC Chromatogram of Red Soil Isolate

ATR-FTIR Analysis of Microbial Lovastatin:

The structural characterization of the extracted microbial products from *Aspergillus terreus* was conducted using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy to identify key functional groups. The

resulting spectra for samples RSI (Figure 7) and RFI (Figure 8), exhibited several characteristic peaks that align with the chemical framework of lovastatin (Al-Sa'ady and Aziz, 2021; Balraj et al., 2018). Both samples displayed a broad, intense absorption band in

the 3200-3500 cm^{-1} region, confirming the presence of hydroxyl (O-H) stretching vibrations. In the aliphatic C-H stretching region, sample RSI (Figure 7) showed peaks at 3001.24 cm^{-1} , 2947.23 cm^{-1} , and 2837.29 cm^{-1} , while sample RFI (Figure 8) presented prominent peaks at 2980.02 cm^{-1} and 2841.15 cm^{-1} (Balraj et al., 2018).

Fig.7

Figure 7: FTIR Spectrum of Microbial Extract from Red Soil Isolate

Fig. 8

Figure 8: FTIR Spectrum of Microbial Extract from Rice Farm Isolate

Conversely, RFI (Figure 8) showed a significant peak at 1645.28 cm^{-1} , a shift indicating the presence of the hydroxy acid form of the molecule or the influence of strong hydrogen bonding (Al-Sa'ady and Aziz, 2021; Balraj et al., 2018). Within the fingerprint region, both samples shared a remarkably sharp and strong peak at 1016.49 cm^{-1} , serving as a primary identifier for C-O stretching in the pyran-derived ring (Balraj et al., 2018). Furthermore, RSI (Figure 7) displayed additional ester-related peaks at 1271.09 cm^{-1} and 1178.51 cm^{-1} , while RFI (Figure 8) was characterized by a distinct peak at 1085.92 cm^{-1} . Collectively, these spectroscopic findings provide robust evidence that the microbial extracts from the *Aspergillus terreus* isolates contain the essential structural components of lovastatin.

DISCUSSION

This study confirms the pharmaceutical potential of Maharashtra's soil through the isolation of two *Aspergillus terreus* strains, RFI (rice farm isolate) and RSI (red soil isolate). Morphological characterization

Analysis of the carbonyl (C=O) region revealed distinct chemical environments for each sample: RSI (Figure 7) exhibited two clear peaks at 1747.51 cm^{-1} and 1703.14 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the lactone and ester carbonyl groups, respectively (Al-Sa'ady and Aziz, 2021).

identified both isolates by their signature cinnamon-brown colonies. Analytical validation via TLC (R_f 0.66 for RFI and 0.65 for RSI) and UV-Visible spectrophotometry (λ_{max} 240nm) confirmed the presence of lovastatin's hexahydro-naphthalene ring system.

HPLC analysis further supported these findings, with retention times of 3.14 (RFI) and 2.43 minutes (RSI) indicating varying concentrations of the lactone and β -hydroxy acid forms. Quantitatively, RFI proved superior with a yield of 530 mg/100 ml, while RSI produced 410 mg/100 ml in Czapek Dox broth. These results demonstrate that local soil-derived fungi serve as robust, sustainable bio-factories, offering a natural and "green" alternative to synthetic chemical synthesis for cholesterol control.

CONCLUSION

This research successfully isolated and characterized lovastatin-producing *Aspergillus terreus* strains from natural soil habitats in Maharashtra, confirming their

efficiency as platforms for microbial metabolite production through TLC, UV-Vis, HPLC, and ATR-FTIR analysis. The Rice Farm Isolate (RFI) emerged as the superior producer with a high yield of 530 mg/100 ml, while the Red Soil Isolate (RSI) yielded 410 mg/100 ml and demonstrated a definitive structural match to the lovastatin framework. These findings validate that diverse natural habitats are viable sources for robust wild-type isolates, supporting a transition toward sustainable, cost-effective, and "green" pharmaceutical manufacturing as a natural alternative to complex chemical synthesis.

Future Aspects

To advance the industrial viability of these local *Aspergillus terreus* isolates, future research should focus on statistical media optimization via Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to surpass current yields. Enhancing metabolic efficiency through genetic strain improvement via mutagenesis and scaling production from rotary flasks to large-scale stirred-tank bioreactors is essential for evaluating commercial feasibility. Additionally, investigating Solid State Fermentation (SSF) using local agricultural residues and refining downstream purification protocols will further reduce operational costs while ensuring pharmaceutical-grade purity.

Acknowledgement

We express our sincere gratitude to our guide, Professor Shradha Shukla, for her invaluable mentorship and expertise throughout the isolation and characterization of our *Aspergillus terreus* strains. Special thanks to Dr. Mahadev Jadhav, Head of the Department of Biotechnology at Deogiri College, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, for providing essential laboratory facilities and continuous leadership. We also appreciate the faculty and technical staff for their assistance during the analytical phases, specifically the TLC, UV-Vis, HPLC, and ATR-FTIR analyses. Finally, we thank our families and friends for their unwavering support during our final year research, "Microbial production of lovastatin: a bioprospecting and green pharmaceutical approach".

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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